

Yield performance of some promising dryland rice cultivars in São Paulo, Brazil.^a

Cultivar	Mean yield (t/ha), 11 environments			$\sqrt{s_d^2}$	\bar{r}	Mean yield (t/ha), 10 environments			$\sqrt{s_d^2}$	\bar{r}	Mean yield (t/ha), 21 environments		
	b					b					b		
IAC25	2.2 a	1	0.4	0.1	2.3 a	0.9	1.2**	-0.01	2.3 a	0.9	0.8**	0.08	
IAC41	1.9 b	1	0.3		2.3 a	1.0	0.8**		2.1 a	1	0.6*		
P. Precoce	2.0 b	0.9	0.4		2.2 a	0.9	1.2**		2.1 a	1.1	0.8**		
Batatais	1.9 bc	0.8	0.2		2.3 a	1.1	1.2**		2.1 a	1.0	0.8**		
IAC5032	1.9 cd	0.0	0.2		2.0 a	1.0	0.7*		1.9 a	1.0	0.5		
IAC1246	1.8 cd	1.1	0.2		2.0 a	1.0	0.6*		1.9 a	1.0	0.5		
IAC1131	1.8 cd	1.1	0.3		2.0 a	1.0	0.8**		1.9 a	1.1	0.5		
IAC5544	1.8 d	1.1	0.3		2.0 a	1.0	0.7**		1.9 a	1.1	0.5		
\bar{x}	1.9	1.0	0.3		2.1	1.0	0.9		2.0	1.0	0.6		

^a5% and ^{**}1% levels of significance. Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

^band $\sqrt{s_d^2}$ = parameters of stability. \bar{r} = mean correlation coefficient.

Gr₁ — Campinas, Tiete, Tatui, and Capao Bonito counties — and Gr₂ — Mococa, Pindorama, Kibeirao Preto, Guaira, and Jau counties (see figure). Linear and nonlinear components of G × E interactions and the mean correlation coefficient for grain yield were calculated for each group.

Pooled analysis of variance showed that the G × E, G × Gn₁, and G × Gr₂ interactions were highly significant. Despite having the lowest mean yield, Gr₁ showed an interaction variance

component 5 times lower than G × E interactions. The high value of the mean correlation coefficient for this group characterizes it as a homogenous subregion.

On the basis of environment mean values, Gr₁ showed cultivar differences as well as the lowest mean yield. The highest overall mean yield was for IAC25 in Gr₂ and the lowest was for IAC5544 in Gr₁. The data on yield, mean correlation coefficient, and two parameters of stability are given in the

table.

Good adaptability of cultivars, except for Batatais in the homogenous subregion, was indicated by the linear regression coefficients. IAC25, IAC47, Pratao Precoce, and Batatais yields were stable. But IAC 25 productivity and Batatais adaptation to unfavorable environments capability must be excluded from the homogenous condition. The inconsistent performance of all cultivars in the heterogenous subregion also should be excluded. ■

Yield and yield-contributing characters of photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties and their ratoons

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The yielding ability of ratoon and main crop of three photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties — FR 13A, SR26B, and Achra 108/1 — grown in the dry (boro) season were compared. The ratoons were higher than the main crop in all varieties (see table). Differences in effective tiller number and panicle length were small. Grain yields were less in ratoons than in main crops (see figure).

No relationship was found in yielding ability of the main crop and its ratoon. However, Achra 108/1 and SR26B had higher total yields.

Yield difference in SR26B between the main crop and the ratoon crop could be accounted for by lower grain numbers per panicle, lower 1,000 grain weight, and higher sterility.

Plant height, tiller number, and panicle length in main and ratoon crops of 3 photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties in West Bengal, India-

Variety	Plant height (cm)		Tiller no.		Panicle length (cm)	
	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon	Main crop	Ratoon
FR13A	120	154	9	9	28	25
SR26B	136	172	9	7	26	27
Achra 108/1	129	185	8	8	26	28

Yield (t/ha)

Grain yield of 3 photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties and their ratoons